

Supplementary Figure 1. The kynurenine pathway of tryptophan metabolism. AA, anthranilic acid; ACMS, amino- β -carboxymuconate-6-semialdehyde; ACMSD, amino- β -carboxymuconate-semialdehyde-decarboxylase; AMS, 2-aminomuconic-6-semialdehyde; fKyn, formyl-kynurenine; HAA, 3-hydroxyanthranilic acid; HAAO, 3-hydroxyanthranilic acid 3,4-dioxygenase; IDO, indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase; HK, 3-hydroxykynurenine; IL-1 β , Interleukin-1 β ; Interleukin-6, IL-6, INFs, interferons; KA, kynurenic acid; KAT, kynurenine aminotransferase; KMO, kynurenine-3-monooxygenase; Kyn, kynurenine; KYNU, Kynureninase; Pic, picolinic acid; QA, quinolinic acid; Qld, quinaldic acid; XA, xanthurenic acid; TDO, tryptophan 2,3-dioxygenase; TNF- α , tumor necrosis factor- α ; Trp, tryptophan.

Factor analysis

Factor analysis was performed on a subset of the biomarkers; the kynurenines, PLP, the protein biomarkers, CRP, SAA, S100A and cystatin C, and the covariates smoking and body mass index (BMI). Three factors with an eigenvalue well above one could reliably be extracted. We chose to present a two-factor solution where the two factors explained 40.3 % of the total variation (a third factor only increased the total explained variation to 47.0%). To further simplify the solution, we removed S100A and BMI which loaded only weakly on the two factors. Scores from the two factors were used to generate a score-plot with individual scores labeled by Graves disease (GD) status. The association between factor scores and presence of GD was quantified by using GD status to predict the scaled scores adjusted for sample storage. The results of those analyses are given as difference (Δ) in scaled score values ($-\log_{10}(\text{P-value})$) between GD and healthy controls. The association of the two factors with biomarker ratios were evaluated in a similar manner using linear regression on the scores with effect measure standardized regression coefficient ($-\log_{10}(\text{P-value})$).

Figure 2 (main manuscript) shows the factor analysis of selected biomarkers labeled by outcome status (GD or healthy control). Loading pattern of the different biomarkers on factors 1 and 2 are shown in Supplementary Figure 2. The two-factor solution indicates that variations in kynurenine levels are organized roughly along two axes. Factor 1 is dominated by positive loadings (i.e., close correlation) of the side-branch metabolites Pic, KA and XA. The same factor also shows negative loadings of the acute phase inflammatory markers CRP and SAA. In contrast, factor 2 was dominated by strong loadings of Kyn, QA, and HK. We interpret this factor as representing inflammatory activation whereby Kyn is increased upon activation of IDO, and HK upon a simultaneous activation of kynurenine-3-monooxygenase (KMO), ultimately directing the kynurenine metabolism towards increased generation of QA. As further confirmation of this interpretation we found that the Kyn/Trp ratio (KTR) was associated with factors 1 and 2 with β z-score ($-\log_{10}(\text{P-value})$) of -0.22 (5.7) and 0.78 (40), respectively. Notably, GD was strongly associated with factor 2 as shown on Figure 2 (main manuscript) with association strength 0.80 (7.3).

Figure 2 adopted from main manuscript

Supplementary Figure 2: Loading pattern of the two-factor solution. The sequence of items along the factors were determined by hierarchical cluster analysis on a distance matrix based on the unadjusted correlation of the biomarkers, as visualized by the dendrogram.

HKr

Supplementary Figure 3. Combined distribution and box plots showing all biomarkers values for controls vs Graves' disease (cases) (red spots; hyperthyroid, blue spots; euthyroid).